

BOOST D4.5: Inter-platform/archive workflows and potential use cases for RO-Crate

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Document History

Issue	Date	Comment	Editor
Draft	28/04/25	Circulated to EDS and DAPI Platform partners for comment	Esther Conway
V1.0	30/04/25	Updated after comments from PDC, DAFNI, UKCEH and CEDA	Esther Conway

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Introduction

NERC has managed data access and sharing policies since its creation in 1965. Today, the Environmental Data Service (EDS)¹ provides integrated data services across its five data centres, including operational analysis platforms, across all NERC² domains. Most science applications are becoming increasingly multidisciplinary; The EDS is working towards providing environmental data users with a “one stop shop” for data services. The EDS forms part of NERC’s digital strategy and implementation, working across discipline boundaries to break down barriers and facilitate data sharing.

The EDS, with partners, will pilot cloud native FAIR data services to support cross-disciplinary, pan-UKRI applications which increasingly need to combine diverse data and knowledge of the underpinning measurement and data capabilities. These services will extend our DRI Phase 1b developments of core NERC data services, building on international standards and data commons principles to link to existing cross-council DRI developments. The BOOST project will address:

- Data findability and traceability through Persistent Identifier registration and asset cataloguing with a novel linking of provenance via semantic graphing techniques.
- Extend data accessibility and interoperability by continuing to develop a federated Trusted Research Environment on JASMIN, ensuring compliance with DARE UK standards.
- By building on the EDS DataLabs data processing environment, create workflow services to process, quality assure and integrate large-scale genomics data that describe biodiversity.
- Enhance interoperability across disciplines by performing a detailed review of analysis platforms across disciplines and user applications, leading to recommendations for FAIR implementation.

Support all of the above through a coordinated framework of co-creation of services and associated training with users.

¹ <https://eds.ukri.org/environmental-data-service>

² <https://www.ukri.org/councils/nerc/>

This document is concerned with activities on Work Package 4 which performed a review of Analysis Platforms with Recommendations for Interoperation. NERC and UKRI have many data analysis platforms designed to accommodate individual communities, workflows and available resources. We will exploit the RDA³ framework, emerging global trans-disciplinary standards and also develop links with CEOS⁴ and other trailblazing community groups to establish best practice. The recommendations will inform FAIR data services working within a CARE compliant framework⁵.

Work Package 4 Deliverables:

- BOOST D4.1: Working Group, Workshops, User Survey and Key Reports
- BOOST D4.2: Progress with establishing a TRE on JASMIN and utilising workflows - May 9th Workshop
- BOOST D4.3: CEOS Jupyter Notebooks Best Practice V1.1
- BOOST D4.4: NERC DataLabs Fair Interoperability
- BOOST D4.5: Inter- platform/archive workflows and use cases for RO-Crates (**This Document**)
- BOOST 4.6: Recommendation for improving the interoperability of Data Analysis Platforms

In this document BOOST D4.4 we consider the importance of workflows connecting up archives and data analysis platforms in parallel to the Work Package 3 efforts. As we discovered from the survey and working group discussions in addition to simply moving data from archive to platform and platform; there is the need to extract, transform, compress data and document uncertainties associated with any transformation. We cover key technologies such as RO-Crates⁶, Common workflow language⁷ Cloud optimized formats. We also look at a complex exemplar from the Polar Data Centre connecting multiple archives and platforms that is able to generate a RO-Crate. We then explore some key areas that would form inter-platform/archive workflows that would benefit from a pilot project.

³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

⁴ <https://ceos.org/>

⁵ https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5d3799de845604000199cd24/t/6397b363b502ff481fce6baf/1670886246948/CARE%2BPrinciples_One%2BPages%2BFINAL_Oct_17_2019.pdf

⁶ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>

⁷ <https://www.commonwl.org/>

RO Crate Technology Overview

An RO-Crate⁸ is an integrated view through which you can see an entire Research Object⁹; the methods, the data, the output and the outcomes of a project or a piece of work. Linking all this together enables the sharing of research outputs with their context, as a coherent whole.

RO-Crates link data and metadata no matter where they are stored – so that from a paper, you can find the data, and from the data, and critically a workflow that has produced a particular dataset where for example a can be identified and using the ro-crate-py package¹⁰. RO-crates can be generated by a workflow run.

Fig1. RO-Crate overview

The RO-Crates originally had most traction within the life sciences domain, being adopted by Elixr¹¹ and used to capture Galaxy workflows¹². They are currently gaining more influence within the environmental sciences community. Critically many projects have had success capturing the types of workflow we would wish to recreate carrying out data extraction using data cubes/Zarr. They additionally can capture workflows that reformat, rescale, reproject data whilst capturing documentation on uncertainties from these actions. They also have established success with projects using ADES and Jupyter notebooks as workflow engines.

⁸ https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/about_ro_crate

⁹ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/background#research-object-background>

¹⁰ <https://github.com/ResearchObject/ro-crate-py>

¹¹ <https://elixiruknode.org/service/ro-crate/>

¹² <https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/topics/fair/tutorials/ro-crate-workflow-run-ro-crate/tutorial.html>

Common Workflow Language

One of the key things we would like to achieve is the ability to rerun a workflow from an RO-Crate. This would mean using a tool that can interpret the RO-Crate metadata and re-execute the workflow based on the information within. This would involve mapping the RO-Crate's input parameters to a workflow language, like CWL, and then running the workflow on the specified inputs. The ability to re-run a workflow is consequential on two fronts. Firstly in efficing of scientific analysis where scientists would gain the ability to share and recreate common processing runs which can easily be adapted. The second is through opening up data to new types of user, where they may not have the skills to develop their own workflows but would benefit greatly from data produced by it.

The Common Workflow Language (CWL)¹³ is an open standard for describing how to run command line tools and connect them to create workflows. Tools and workflows described using CWL are portable across a variety of platforms that support the CWL standards. Using CWL, it can be used to scale complex data analysis and machine learning workflows from a single developer's laptop up to massively parallel cluster, cloud and high performance computing environments. This breadth of application is attractive to EDS in terms of the range of workflow we may wish to support.

The other component to consider is where to key workflows we would currently advocate the use of Workflow Hub¹⁴. It can currently be used by anyone who wants to share, register, and discover computational workflow. It can also support RO-Crates, CWL and FAIR standards.

¹³ <https://www.commonwl.org/>

¹⁴ <https://workflowhub.eu/>

Cloud Optimization

Cloud-optimized formats are file formats designed for efficient storage, access, and processing of data, especially geospatial data, in cloud environments. They leverage the scalability and parallel processing capabilities of cloud infrastructure, enabling efficient handling of large datasets. Given the heterogeneous nature of EDS data holding we would need to assess the benefits and cut off point of using different formats for which type of data holdings. It is important to consider that for many smaller specialist datasets that cloud optimized may not be what is required. An important recommendation is to ascertain when and where these formats should be considered in terms of EDS holdings.

The types of format we need to investigate in terms of cloud optimization are as follows.

Zarr¹⁵: Zarr is an open standard for storing large multidimensional array data. It specifies a protocol and data format, and is designed to be "cloud ready" including random access, by dividing data into subsets referred to as chunks. Zarr is designed to support high-throughput distributed I/O on different storage systems, which is a common requirement in cloud computing.

CFA¹⁶ (Climate Forecast Aggregation): CFA is a convention used to aggregate climate forecast data for access to NetCDF data in object storage systems. It is designed to enable NetCDF-based aggregations by referencing array fragments in multiple files within object storage, making it suitable for large datasets like climate forecasts. CFA maintains the CF-conventions for aggregated data, including self-descriptive objects at all levels, in contrast to Zarr which includes many small non-descriptive data files.

COG¹⁷ (Cloud Optimized GeoTIFF): COG is a specialized version of the GeoTIFF raster image format designed for efficient access and use in cloud environments. It is optimized for serving large raster datasets over HTTP using range requests, enabling clients to request only the necessary portions of a file.

GeoJSON¹⁸: GeoJSON is an open standard format designed for representing simple geographical features, along with their non-spatial attributes. It is based on the JSON format and can be used for vector and point cloud data.

¹⁵ <https://zarr.dev/>

¹⁶ <https://techblog.ceda.ac.uk/2021/12/08/cfa-conventions-intro.html>

¹⁷ <https://cogeo.org/>

¹⁸ <https://geojson.org/>

GeoParquet¹⁹: Geo Parquet is a geospatial version of the Parquet format. Apache Parquet is a powerful column-oriented data format, built from the ground up as a modern alternative to CSV files. GeoParquet is an incubating Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) standard that adds interoperable geospatial types (Point, Line, Polygon) to Parquet.

Additionally we may be constrained as archives and need to maintain holding NetCDF5, HDF5, GRIB or Tiff; in which case to be considered cloud-optimized, the archive should consider chunking and compression.

Kerchunk: Kerchunk²⁰ is a library that provides a unified way to represent a variety of chunked, compressed data formats. It allows efficient access to the data from traditional file systems or cloud object storage. It also provides a flexible way to create virtual datasets from multiple files. This means that you can create a virtual aggregate dataset over potentially many source files, for efficient, parallel and cloud-friendly in-situ access without having to copy or translate the originals. It is therefore a gateway to in-the-cloud massive data processing.

There are additionally recent CEDA developments which could be considered by other EDS centres and platforms wishing to access data on CEDA.

PADOCC²¹ (Pipeline to Aggregate Data for Optimised Cloud Capabilities Package): PADOCC is Python tool for creating new data representations/formats to enable greater access to data in the CEDA archive.

DataPoint:²² DataPoint is a Python tool for searching records in Catalogs using the STAC metadata convention, and accessing data of different cloud-optimised formats, while abstracting the configurations for different file types from the user.

¹⁹ <https://geoparquet.org/>

²⁰ <https://techblog.ceda.ac.uk/2023/05/04/kerchunk-experiments.html>

²¹ <https://cedadev.github.io/padocc/>

²² <https://cedadev.github.io/datapoint/>

Inter-platform/archive work flows

In this section we look at a multiplatform workflow exemplar and then progress to discuss candidate areas where we like to investigate workflow that would benefit other platforms and utilise EDS data holdings.

UK Polar Data Centre multi platform exemplar

Thomas Zwagerman of the UK Polar Data Centre²³ (UK PDC) created the asli-pipeline²⁴ for operational execution of the Amundsen Seas Low Indices (ASLI) calculations.

The aim of this exemplar was to create a modular workflow to enable automated and continual publication of a monthly dataset to the UK PDC, as well as capture provenance through the use of RO-Crate.

It was developed to enable deployment on different systems (e.g. JASMIN, BAS HPCs) and work with different file formats, including cloud-optimised formats. In this example, a deployment is demonstrated using a combination of NERC EDS services: JASMIN²⁵, the UK PDC and Datalabs²⁶.

Amundsen Seas Low

The Amundsen Seas Low (ASL) is a highly dynamic and mobile climatological low pressure system located in the Pacific sector of the Southern Ocean. In this sector, variability in sea-level pressure is greater than anywhere in the Southern Hemisphere, making it challenging to isolate local fluctuations in the ASL from larger-scale shifts in atmospheric pressure. The position and strength of the ASL are crucial for understanding regional change over West Antarctica²⁷.

²³ <https://www.bas.ac.uk/data/uk-pdc/>

²⁴ Zwagerman, T., & Wilby, D. (2024). asli-pipeline (0.1.0). Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14552486>

²⁵ <https://jasmin.ac.uk/>

²⁶ <https://eds.ukri.org/tools/datalabs>

²⁷ Hosking, J. S., A. Orr, T. J. Bracegirdle, and J. Turner (2016), Future circulation changes off West Antarctica: Sensitivity of the Amundsen Sea Low to projected anthropogenic forcing, *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 43, 367–376, doi:10.1002/2015GL067143.

Fig 2. Example plot showing the location of the Amundsen Sea Low, within the Amundsen Sea sector. Shown alongside the Antarctic mainland in Polar Stereographic projection²⁸.

Therefore, it is beneficial to continually publish ASL data, as it can be a crucial input parameter to improve environmental forecasting systems.

Leveraging NERC EDS Services

The ASLI results are calculated using ERA5's mean sea-level pressure data, available on the Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS)²⁹. To enable continuous publication to the UK PDC, we deployed asli-pipeline to perform calculations, data transfer and quality control tasks automatically.

The diagram overleaf illustrates the pipeline and shows the flow and transformation of data between the CDS and NERC EDS Services..

²⁸ https://scotthosking.com/asl_index

²⁹ Copernicus Climate Change Service (2023): ERA5 hourly data on single levels from 1940 to present. Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS), DOI: 10.24381/cds.adbb2d47.

Below, the different NERC EDS services and how they were used in the asli-pipeline deployment are described.

JASMIN: Pipeline Execution and Object Storage

To generate the ASLI dataset, the asli-pipeline is deployed on JASMIN. It uses the CDS API to read in ERA5 mean sea-level pressure³⁰, perform calculations on LOTUS using the `asli` python package³¹, and moves results to S3 buckets on the JASMIN Object Store. It also moves data to a location accessible to the UK PDC, where the dataset can be published and minted with a Digital Object Identifier (DOI).

Datalabs: User Interaction and Application Hosting

Object Store Buckets on JASMIN enable access through the Datalabs platform³², which also has web app hosting capabilities.

An RStudio notebook is used to host a small demonstrator R Shiny app, asliapp³³, which allows the user to view and interact with the “live” ASLI dataset. The purpose of this app is merely to demonstrate the interaction between Datalabs and JASMIN, and has no other purpose. However, more complex use cases can leverage the benefits of using object storage to efficiently interact with large datasets in cloud-optimised file formats.

UK Polar Data Centre: Storing Dataset in Perpetuity

The asli-pipeline moved ASLI calculations results to a location that can be accessed by the UK PDC, to allow continuous publication. However, our results are derived from an external data source. This means we rely on its continuity. In ERA5’s case, there have been occasional issues with input data that have forced a recalculation^{34 35}, meaning previously published data differs from the final product.

In a pipeline that continually updates and publishes a derived dataset, it should be ensured that previous input data changing (e.g. an ERA5 recalculation) does not affect previously published outputs. If there are changes to previously published data, and we append our existing dataset, anyone attempting to reproduce our methods would get different results. The dataset’s DOI will be invalidated, and it will be necessary to supersede it.

³⁰ Hersbach, H., Bell, B., Berrisford, P., Biavati, G., Horányi, A., Muñoz Sabater, J., Nicolas, J., Peubey, C., Radu, R., Rozum, I., Schepers, D., Simmons, A., Soci, C., Dee, D., Thépaut, J-N. (2018): ERA5 hourly data on single levels from 1940 to present. Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS), DOI: 10.24381/cds.adbb2d47.

³¹ Hosking, J. S., & Wilby, D. asli [Computer software]. <https://github.com/scotthosking/amundsen-sea-low-index>

³² Brown, M. J., & Chevuturi, A. object_store_tutorial [Computer software]. https://github.com/NERC-CEH/object_store_tutorial

³³ <https://github.com/antarctica/asliapp>

³⁴ <https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/CKB/ERA5T+issue+in+snow+depth>

³⁵ <https://forum.ecmwf.int/t/final-validated-era5-product-to-differ-from-era5t-in-july-2024/6685>

To account for this, asli-pipeline incorporates a quality control and verification step to ensure previously published data remains unchanged before it is transferred to the UK PDC. The R package "butterfly"³⁶ was developed for this purpose, and incorporated into the asli-pipeline as a failsafe³⁷.

Should there be an unexpected change, the user is warned and data transfer is stopped. The next step would be to make the published dataset static by changing its title and description to a fixed date, as we are now no longer appending it. It should then be superseded with the latest version, and the process restarted. The added value of using RO-Crate

An example RO-Crate .json file of this work is provided in the annex. Summarising why RO-Crate provides added value in this example:

- Processing steps taken by the workflow are captured. This includes project setup, configuration files and input data source and version, making it easier to reproduce.
- Different software packages (e.g. asli, asli-pipeline, butterfly) and their respective versions, which were developed to support this work, can be attached. Appropriate and specific attribution can be given to authors' contributions.
- The published data, and its version, can be attached along with other associated outputs, such as an R Shiny Application.

³⁶ Zwagerman, T. (2024). "butterfly: quality assurance of continually updating and overwritten time-series data." [Computer Software]. <https://github.com/ropensci/butterfly>

³⁷ Incorporating butterfly in an operational pipeline: https://docs.ropensci.org/butterfly/articles/butterfly_in_pipeline.html

Candidate areas for inter-archive/platform workflows

	NOC Data Analysis Platform	JASMIN	DAFNI	EODH	NERC Data Labs	Polar Digital Twin	CReDo	Health TRE
British Oceanographic Data Centre	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	White
Centre for Environmental Data Analysis	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue
Environmental Information Data Centre	White	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	White	Blue	Blue
National Geoscience Data Centre	White	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	White	Blue	Blue
Polar Data Centre	Blue	Blue	White	Blue	Blue	Blue	White	White

Table 1. Areas for development of inter-archive/platform workflows

Through workgroup discussion we identified areas that we should investigate further in terms of EDS providing users of different platforms with data feeds from re-executable workflows. In the above matrix we considered which data centres were most likely to provide impactful data feeds to which platforms to stimulate more targeted discussions. The blue rectangles in the above matrix are areas where workflows connecting archives and data analysis platforms should be developed.

This is an additional activity which goes beyond initial scope of the project but we felt it was an area that merited further investigation. We summarise some of the early discussion we have had as indication of where we would like to go next if we were to secure funding for a full inter-archive/platform pilot.

DAFNI

The STFC programme Data Analysis Facility for National Infrastructure (DAFNI³⁸) is a national facility for data analysis and collaborative model and workflow development for the infrastructure research community.

The platform works with academic researchers across multiple domains to support world leading infrastructure system research within the UK. The platform is free to use for researchers and ensures that researchers have a place to collaborate and share research outputs and data.

DAFNI enables the research community to generate new insights at a high level of detail and accuracy. One of the core activities is the sharing and execution of computational models that support infrastructure research.

Below are two types of DAFNI model that would benefit from EDS data.

The OpenCLIM HEAT model is a heat extremes analysis tool, for the integration of heatwave and related temperature and heat stress extremes analysis with other climate risk modelling. It uses Daily mean temperature (TMean) taken from the UK Met Office's UKCP18 twelve member regional climate model (RCM) ensemble at 12 km resolution. In anticipation of other models that require climate projection, the ability of CEDA to be able to supply data from key Climate data sets such as from CMIP6 or the high resolution EOCIS land surface temperature³⁹ into models of this type is of importance.

The 5G Model is a model to estimate the demand for and cost of rolling out 5G across the UK for a variety of different population and demand scenarios. Its inputs are data from a CSV file, containing location of the cell towers, population density, geology for sites of base stations, and estimated data growth. Data sources for cell tower locations can be downloaded from <https://opencellid.org/> and integrated into the CSV format for the model. Again, the ability to deliver geophysical data into this type of model from the British Geophysical data centre adds value to this model.

³⁸ <https://www.dafni.ac.uk/>

³⁹ <https://catalogue.ceda.ac.uk/uuid/a784eeb9287b43bcb63ccae59e6af82e/>

National Oceanographic Centre Interactive Data Analysis Platform

The National Ocean Data Centre is currently testing a small deployment running on a recycled on-prem server with a small number of users, a mix of use cases, and research areas which include for example satellite image analysis.

- Spare server with:
 - o 2x 28 core Intel 6132 CPU
 - o 3.5TB disk
 - o 384GB RAM
 - o 2x NVIDIA P100 GPU with 16GB VRAM each
- Enough for 10s of simultaneous users
- GPU supports AI/ML and image analysis applications
- JupyterHub running on Docker
- Configured using Salt stack
- PAM/LDAP authentication to our LDAP server
- GPFS home/group directories mounted
- Users can access most of the data/conda environments they would normally use on other servers.

SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The ability to reuse standard workflow to extract only the data needed from satellite CEDA holdings on JASMIN, and to reformat/reproject/reshape/rescale in a way that is complementary to British Oceanographic Data Centre holdings, has the potential for efficiency savings in both storage and analysis time.

NERC DataLabs

DataLabs⁴⁰ is a cloud-based digital platform designed to support collaborative, open, transparent, and data-driven science. It allows users to flexibly combine multiple elements within one integrated 'environment', and for this reason it is sometimes classified as a Virtual Research Environment (VRE). For the avoidance of confusion, DataLabs is the name of both the platform and individual projects (DataLabs within DataLabs). Each project integrates a unique combination of digital assets – data, models, methods, code, visualisations, etc. – which are then used to answer environmental research questions and support decision making.

The asli pipe-line described above is just one example of the type of workflow that could supply the diverse communities with a range of data from national and international sources. The multiplatform workflows are a way of getting platforms to work together collaboratively to avoid the need for duplication of function or resource. The modularisation developed in work package 3 also promises efficiency savings for the scientific community. Another thing to note is that there are many simple workflows doing things like format conversion. These would be of great value in terms of time savings and lowering barriers for new/inexperienced users from different domains.

⁴⁰ <https://eds.ukri.org/tools/datalabs>

JASMIN

JASMIN⁴¹ is a globally-unique data analysis facility. It provides storage and compute facilities to enable data-intensive environmental science. Over 1500 users are currently supported exploring topics ranging from climate change and oceanography to air pollution, earthquake deformation and analysis of wildlife populations.

Service groups

Centred more around storage and data analysis than a “traditional” supercomputer, JASMIN provides flexibility for a wide range of data-intensive analysis workflows. Tens of petabytes of storage are combined with several types of compute resource: managed interactive and batch compute for building and executing large workflows, and a “community cloud” offering projects and communities a set of service components with which to build and manage their own computing needs. All with high-performance access to massive data resources, including the curated archives of the Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA).

Given the flexibility to support this wide range of data-intensive workflows, the ability to capture these workflows for re-use by other members of the community has the potential for great efficiency savings. We have had repeated requests from early researchers to have access to workflows for common processes on JASMIN. The other thing to note is that during data set acquisition for the last LTSS NCEO phase nearly half of researchers stated that the ability to capture and rerun the processes that generated was nearly more important than the dataset itself. This finding was repeated in the survey results. The modularisation approach developed in Work Package 3 will also support the capture of important workflow elements for reuse in other processes.

⁴¹ <https://jasmin.ac.uk/about/>

Earth Observation Data Hub

The Earth Observation Data (EODH)⁴² hub ran in a very similar timeframe to the BOOST project. The overall goal of the Earth Observation Data Hub project was to develop and operate a new centralised software infrastructure – DataHub – to provide a new ‘single point’ of access for UK EO data offerings from distributed public and commercial centres.

I can now provide a single point of access to a range of important Earth Observation data. It can now provide a standard common set of services and APIs upon which new EO services and tools can be developed and accessed by the UK EO data community. This pathfinder project has brought new thinking and experimental developments that will result in practical services.

We are now hoping that the EODH is extended to a second phase as a number of its achievements are of interest to the BOOST working group members. Exploring the use of ADES workflows to supply CMIP6, EO Satellite data and EOCIS high resolution products to platforms serving a number of domains would be desirable. Also, the ability to combine a range of environmental data with satellite data as a QGIS layer in order to make it more usable by environmental consultants and governmental departments is something we would wish to pursue.

Polar Digital Twin

Digital Twins (DTs) are already in operation in industry and involve highly interoperable data pipelines, optimisation, and a mixture of knowledge-informed and data-driven probabilistic machine learning and artificial intelligence (AI). DTs are increasingly becoming a key component for research discovery, education, and aiding discussions at the board-level without having to wait weeks to months for results from traditional computer models. BAS scientists and engineers are identifying future requirements for Digital Twins of the Antarctic and Arctic natural environments, polar research bases, BAS research ship the RRS Sir David Attenborough and autonomous marine vehicles. By collaborating with a wide range of international research institutes and businesses their aim is to support international efforts to develop a Digital Twin Earth⁴³.

We would anticipate that data from the EDS such as the EOCIS land sea and ice datasets⁴⁴ would have application in this area.

⁴² <https://eodahub.org.uk/>

⁴³ <https://www.bas.ac.uk/project/digital-twins-of-the-polar-regions/#about>

⁴⁴ <https://eocis.org/2025/02/06/applications-of-the-eocis-land-ice-and-sea-ice-datasets/>

Climate Resilience Demonstrator

The Climate Resilience Demonstrator (CReDo)⁴⁵ is a pioneering digital twin platform for climate change adaptation that improves system-wide resilience across infrastructure networks. CReDo leverages digital twin technology to help infrastructure owners and operators respond to extreme climate scenarios, preventing potential asset failures across sectors. By understanding infrastructure interdependencies, the project will enhance decision-making regarding infrastructure investment, thus reducing the costs associated with repairs and helping society maintain essential services during extreme weather.

Again CReDo is in the early stages of the project and made contact through Elliot Christou of the Connected Places Catapult. Given the digital twins requirement for information on extreme weather events and climate change, they have expressed an interest in EDS data and workflow we can produce to fuel a digital twin or support the analysis of their outputs.

Health TREs

We held a meeting with DARE UK in relation to the Work Package 2 effort where we initially planned to set up a SATRE compliant TRE on JASMIN. The conversation then progressed to workflows given some of the limitations of software that could be installed with a TRE, and the fact that there is unlikely to be a TRE in every archive and there will always be resistance to some highly sensitive data being moved out of its original secure environment. To that end we have scheduled a workshop on May 9th to discuss further. However, even at this point there are strong indications that a lot of climate and environmental data will be valuable to the health scientist if we can successfully deliver it to them in a usable form.

⁴⁵ <https://cp.catapult.org.uk/project/climate-resilience-demonstrator-credo/>

Annex A: RO-Crate .json file

```
@context      "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.1/context"
@graph
0
@id      "."
@type "Dataset"
datePublished "2024-12-19T16:01:50+00:00"
hasPart
0
@id      "data/"
1
@id      "ENVS"
2
@id      "output/"
3
@id      "src/"
4
@id      "run_asli_pipeline.sh"
1
@id      "ro-crate-metadata.json"
@type "CreativeWork"
about
@id      "."
conformsTo
@id      "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.1"
2
@id      "data/"
@type "Dataset"
description      "Folder containing ERA5 land sea mask (era5_lsm.nc) and ERA5/monthly/era5_mean_sea_level_pressure_monthly_*.nc files."
encodingFormat      "application/netcdf"
name      "ERA5 Data"
type      "FormalParameter"
valueRequired true
3
@id      "ENVS"
@type "File"
name      "Pipeline Configuration File"
type      "FormalParameter"
valueRequired true
4
```

```

@id "output/"
@type "Dataset"
author
@id "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3646-3504"
datePublished "<built-in method isoformat of datetime.datetime object at 0x715a7b1342d0>"
encodingFormat "text/csv"
name "ASL Calculations"
type "FormalParameter"
5
@id "src/"
@type "Dataset"
author
@id "https://orcid.org/0009-0003-3742-3234"
name "pipeline scripts"
programming_language
0
@id "Python"
1
@id "bash"
2
@id "r"
type
0 "File"
1 "SoftwareSourceCode"
url "https://github.com/antarctica/asli-pipeline"
6
@id "run_asli_pipeline.sh"
@type "File"
author
@id "https://orcid.org/0009-0003-3742-3234"
description "Pipeline using asli python package to calculate ASL Indices"
input
0
@id "data/"
1
@id "ENVS"
2
@id "#asli_package"
3
@id "#butterfly_package"
4
@id "src/"
name "ASLI Pipeline"

```

```

output
@id "output/"
type
0 "File"
1 "SoftwareSourceCode"
2 "ComputationalWorkflow"
url "https://github.com/antarctica/asli-pipeline"
7
@id "Download ERA5 data"
@type "CreateAction"
agent
@id "https://orcid.org/0009-0003-3742-3234"
description "Script downloading the era5 land sea mask (era5_lsm.nc) and mean sea level
pressure data (data/ERA5/monthly/era5_mean_sea_level_pressure_*.nc), referencing ENV5 to
obtain query parameters."
endTime "<built-in method isoformat of datetime.datetime object at 0x715a79a70b70>"
instrument
0
@id "src/"
1
@id "ENV5"
name "Downloading required ERA5 data"
object "https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/api"
result
@id "data/"
8
@id "ASLI_Calculation"
@type "CreateAction"
agent
@id "https://orcid.org/0009-0003-3742-3234"
description "Pipeline executing asli python package functionality using the era5 land sea
mask (era5_lsm.nc) and mean sea level pressure data
(data/ERA5/monthly/era5_mean_sea_level_pressure_*.nc)"
endTime "<built-in method isoformat of datetime.datetime object at 0x715a7a338480>"
instrument
0
@id "run_asli_pipeline.sh"
1
@id "src/"
name "Running ASLI Calculations on ERA5 data"
object
@id "data/"
result

```

```

@id "output/"
9
@id "#python"
@type "ProgrammingLanguage"
url
0 "https://www.python.org/release/python-3124/"
version"3.12.4"
10
@id "r"
@type "ProgrammingLanguage"
url
0 "https://cran.r-project.org/src/base/R-4/R-4.4.2.tar.gz"
version"4.4.2"
11
@id "#bash"
@type "ProgrammingLanguage"
version"5.2.21(1)-release"
12
@id "#asli_package"
@type "SoftwareApplication"
author
0
@id "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6553-8739"
1
@id "https://orcid.org/0009-0003-3742-3234"
name "asli"
programming_language
@id "Python"
type
0 "File"
1 "SoftwareSourceCode"
url "https://github.com/davidwilby/amundsen-sea-low-index"
version"asli @ git+https://github.com/davidwilby/amundsen-sea-low-
index@0f3a9992b7437687acea8b35f3af882337a211c6"
13
@id "#butterfly_package"
@type "SoftwareApplication"
author
@id "https://orcid.org/0009-0003-3742-3234"
name "butterfly"
programming_language
@id "r"
type

```

0 "File"
1 "SoftwareSourceCode"
url "https://github.com/antarctica/butterfly"
version"1.0.0"
14
@id "https://ror.org/01rhff309"
@type "Organisation"
name "British Antarctic Survey"
url "https://ror.org/01rhff309"
15
@id "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6553-8739"
@type "Person"
affiliation
@id "https://ror.org/01rhff309"
name "David Wilby"
16
@id "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3646-3504"
@type "Person"
affiliation
@id "https://ror.org/01rhff309"
name "Scott Hosking"
17
@id "https://orcid.org/0009-0003-3742-3234"
@type "Person"
affiliation
@id "https://ror.org/01rhff309"
name "Thomas Zwagerman"